

DIGITALIZATION IN PRIMARY HEALTHCARE AND THE IMPACT OF DIGITALIZATION ON THE QUALITY OF STATISTICAL DATA COLLECTION AND THE QUALITY OF MEDICAL CARE

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Abstract. Digitalization of healthcare is one of the key strategies for improving the quality of medical care. The purpose of this study is to assess the impact of digital technologies, such as electronic medical records and telemedicine, on the quality of medical services in primary healthcare in Uzbekistan and Russia. The study included 157 patients using primary health care services in polyclinics of Uzbekistan. The average age of the participants was 44.5 ± 10.2 years. The research methods included questionnaires of patients and doctors, data collection from electronic medical records and analysis of indicators of quality of health care before and after the introduction of digital technologies. For statistical processing of data, paired analysis methods were used using the SPSS version 25.0 program. The introduction of digital technologies reduced the average time to receive medical care from 8.4 to 4.2 days. Patient satisfaction increased from 3.1 to 4.6 points. The frequency of requests for telemedicine consultations increased from 1.2 to 2.7 times per month. The proportion of compliance with medical recommendations increased from 65% to 85%, indicating improved monitoring of patients' condition and compliance with doctors' orders. The results of the study show that digitalization improves interactions between patients and healthcare institutions, accelerates access to healthcare, and increases patient adherence to treatment. Particular attention is paid to telemedicine, which has significantly increased the frequency of patient-physician interactions and improved chronic disease management. However, challenges remain related to staff training and integration of information systems. Digitalization of healthcare has proven its effectiveness in improving the quality of medical care. The introduction of electronic medical records and telemedicine consultations has significantly improved key indicators such as time to receive care, patient satisfaction, and compliance with medical recommendations. For digitalization to be successful, it is necessary to continue training specialists and standardizing medical information systems.

Keywords: digitalization, telemedicine, electronic medical records, primary healthcare, quality of medical care, Uzbekistan.

Introduction

The digitalization of healthcare is actively developing in Russia and Uzbekistan, and in recent years, both countries have made significant steps in this direction. In Russia, the introduction of electronic medical records and telemedicine services has become part of a major program for the digital transformation of healthcare. These technologies facilitate access to medical data, speed up diagnosis and treatment, and reduce the likelihood of errors associated with paper documentation [2]. The national program "Unified Digital Healthcare Contour" is aimed at creating an integrated system that unites all medical institutions to improve interactions between doctors and patients [1].

Digitalization is also a priority in Uzbekistan. The Electronic Healthcare 2025 program aims to create a unified database for all medical institutions, introduce electronic prescriptions and telemedicine services. Important elements of the program include information systems for recording cancer patients (“Cancer Registry”) and platforms for managing sanatorium services (“Electronic Sanatorium”). This project received support from international organizations, including the World Bank, which accelerated its implementation [3,4]. Digitalization improves not only the quality of medical care, but also the collection and analysis of medical data. The introduction of electronic medical records helps reduce the risk of errors and speeds up clinical decision-making. However, problems remain, such as a shortage of qualified specialists and the need to standardize information systems, which require solutions for more successful implementation of technologies [5,7].

Materials and methods

The study involved 157 patients who visited outpatient medical institutions in Uzbekistan from January to September 2023. The average age of patients was 44.5 ± 10.2 years, with a range from 25 to 65 years. The study group included 87 women (55.4%) and 70 men (44.6%). Participants were selected based on the following inclusion criteria: the presence of chronic diseases requiring regular medical monitoring (e.g. hypertension, diabetes mellitus, coronary heart disease) and active use of digital health technologies, such as electronic medical records (EMR) and telemedicine consultations. The study was conducted to assess the impact of digitalization on the quality of medical care in primary health care. The following methods were used to collect data: patient questionnaires, assessment of interaction with medical personnel through digital channels, and analysis of data from the EHR. An important aspect of the study was measuring the time spent on accessing medical information, the timing of diagnosis and initiation of treatment, and the level of patient satisfaction.

The surveys were conducted in a standardized form using validated scales for assessing the quality of medical care, including a patient satisfaction scale and a scale for assessing the availability of medical services. Doctors filled out similar questionnaires, assessing the effectiveness of using digital technologies in their daily practice, including the impact on the speed of clinical decision-making and reducing administrative workload. The collection of objective data was based on information obtained from electronic medical records, including the number of visits, frequency of seeking telemedicine consultations, and compliance with treatment recommendations. To compare the quality of medical care before and after the introduction of digital solutions, the paired analysis method was used.

Statistical data processing was performed using SPSS version 25.0. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was used to check the normality of distribution. Differences between groups were assessed using the Student t-test for independent samples and the Mann-Whitney U-test. The level of statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$. The ethical aspects of the study were strictly observed. All participants were informed about the purpose and methods of the study and gave written consent for the processing of their medical data. The study was approved by the local ethics committee.

Results

The study, based on the analysis of data from 157 patients, showed a significant impact of digitalization on the quality of medical care in primary health care. Table 1 presents the main indicators before and after the introduction of digital technologies.

Table 1

Key indicators of the quality of medical care before and after digitalization

Indicators	Before digitalization	After digitalization
Average time to receive medical care (days)	8.4	4.2
Patient satisfaction (scores)	3.1	4.6
Frequency of requests for telemedicine consultations (once a month)	1.2	2.7
Percentage of compliance with medical recommendations (%)	65	85

The average time to receive medical care has decreased from 8.4 to 4.2 days after the introduction of digital technologies. This is explained by the optimization of processes through the use of electronic medical records and telemedicine consultations, which allow patients to access medical services more quickly.

Patient satisfaction increased from 3.1 to 4.6 points, which confirms the improvement of their interaction with the medical system. Digital solutions have significantly simplified the process of receiving medical care, made it more convenient and accessible, which has had a positive impact on patients' assessment of the services provided.

The frequency of requests for telemedicine consultations increased from 1.2 to 2.7 times per month. This indicates a high level of acceptance of telemedicine among patients, who began to use remote consultations more often to monitor their health. Telemedicine allowed patients to receive timely consultations without having to visit medical institutions, which is especially important for patients with chronic diseases or living in remote areas.

The rate of compliance with medical recommendations also increased significantly from 65% to 85%, which can be attributed to more effective patient monitoring and the ability to remotely monitor their condition. Electronic medical records allowed doctors to better track patients' compliance with prescribed recommendations, and regular telemedicine consultations strengthened adherence to treatment.

Use of telemedicine. One of the key aspects of the study was to examine the role of telemedicine consultations in the process of providing medical care. Before the introduction of digital technologies, the frequency of telemedicine use was extremely low - an average of 1.2 consultations per month per patient. However, after digitalization, this figure more than doubled to 2.7 consultations per month.

Telemedicine has allowed doctors to promptly monitor the condition of patients and provide recommendations for treatment adjustments in real time, which is especially important for patients with chronic diseases. Thanks to digital platforms, patients have been able to seek consultations in a timely manner, avoiding long waits and visits to medical institutions. This has become especially relevant during the pandemic, when the workload on medical institutions has increased significantly. These results confirm that the introduction of telemedicine and digital solutions into the healthcare system not only improves the quality of medical care, but also increases the effectiveness of treatment due to constant monitoring of patients' condition and prompt adjustment of treatment.

Discussion. The results of this study confirm that the introduction of digital technologies into the primary health care system has a significant positive impact on the quality of medical care

provided. An important aspect of this impact is the reduction in the time it takes to receive medical care, improved interaction between patients and health workers, and an increase in the frequency and effectiveness of telemedicine consultations. Digitalization of healthcare is a global trend that is actively supported by the World Health Organization (WHO). According to WHO, the use of digital technologies can significantly improve the availability and quality of medical services, as well as optimize the decision-making process of doctors [8]. In Uzbekistan and Russia, digitalization of healthcare has also become one of the key strategies in the development of medical systems. Programs such as the “Unified Digital Healthcare Contour” in Russia and “Electronic Healthcare 2025” in Uzbekistan are aimed at creating a unified information system that ensures the integration of data from all medical institutions [2,3].

Reducing the time to receive medical care is an important result of the implementation of digital technologies. In the study, the average time to receive medical care was reduced by almost half, which can be explained by the use of electronic medical records (EMR). These cards allow doctors to instantly access medical information about the patient, which significantly speeds up diagnosis and the start of treatment [9]. Similar results were obtained in a number of other studies, where the use of EHR contributed to a reduction in the time for decision-making and a decrease in the number of errors in medical documentation [10].

Increasing patient satisfaction is also one of the key indicators of digitalization effectiveness. In the study, patient satisfaction increased from 3.1 to 4.6 points, which confirms the improvement in the quality of interaction with the medical system. Studies in Russia and Uzbekistan have shown that patients using electronic medical services rate medical care higher than patients using traditional methods of interaction [1,12]. Increased satisfaction is associated with improved access to medical information, simplified appointment booking, and the ability to receive remote consultations.

Of particular note is the increasing frequency of telemedicine use, reflecting the growing popularity of remote methods of interaction between patients and physicians. Telemedicine technologies are actively used in many countries around the world and have proven highly effective in improving access to medical care, especially for patients in remote regions [8,11]. In Uzbekistan and Russia, telemedicine has expanded access to qualified specialists for patients with chronic diseases, which was especially important during the COVID-19 pandemic, when personal visits to medical institutions were limited [6,12].

One of the most important indicators of digitalization is the increase in the proportion of compliance with medical recommendations. During the study, this indicator increased from 65% to 85%, indicating stricter control over the implementation of recommendations by health workers. Electronic medical records and telemedicine consultations allow doctors to promptly monitor the patient's condition and, if necessary, adjust treatment. This is consistent with research conducted in other countries, where the use of digital technologies has increased patient adherence to treatment [9,14].

Despite the positive results, there are also certain challenges associated with the implementation of digital technologies. One of the main problems is the lack of qualified personnel capable of working with new technologies. In Uzbekistan and Russia, as studies have shown, doctors require additional training to effectively use electronic medical systems and telemedicine platforms [13,15]. In addition, problems with the integration of various medical systems and ensuring the confidentiality of patient data remain relevant throughout the world [11,14].

Thus, the results of our study confirm that digitalization of healthcare, in particular the use of electronic medical records and telemedicine, contributes to a significant improvement in the quality of medical care. At the same time, further efforts are needed to train personnel and standardize systems to achieve even higher efficiency rates. The programs implemented in Uzbekistan and Russia can serve as an example of the successful implementation of digital technologies in medical practice.

Conclusion. The results of this study confirm the important role of digitalization in improving the quality of medical care in primary health care. The introduction of electronic medical records, telemedicine and other digital technologies has led to a significant reduction in the time it takes to receive medical services, increased patient satisfaction and improved adherence to treatment. The use of telemedicine platforms has expanded access to medical services, especially in remote areas, which has improved the control of chronic diseases and reduced the burden on medical institutions. Digitalization of healthcare in Russia and Uzbekistan has demonstrated high potential for optimizing medical care. Programs aimed at creating a unified information system have made it possible to integrate data from various medical institutions, which has ensured more effective interaction between doctors and patients. The increased use of telemedicine and improved patient compliance indicate the high efficiency of the technologies being implemented. However, successful implementation of these technologies requires addressing challenges such as training qualified personnel, ensuring the protection of patient data, and further standardization of medical information systems. Despite these challenges, digitalization remains a key tool for improving the quality and accessibility of medical care. The development and implementation of digital technologies in healthcare is not only a pressing task, but also an important area for further improving the efficiency and quality of medical care, especially in the context of growing demands for speed, accuracy and accessibility of medical services in the modern world.

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